

INFORMATION ECONOMY AS THE BASIS FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH AND INCREASING THE LEVEL OF WELL-BEING OF CITIZENS

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Abstract. *In the economic theory of post-industrial society, the information factor is distinguished as a production factor. It is closely related to the achievements of modern science, which has a decisive impact on the level of production efficiency, the process of training a qualified workforce and increasing the potential of human capital. Information provides the systematization of knowledge materialized into a system of mechanisms and machines, equipment, management and marketing models.*

Keywords: *efficiency of the production process, intensive economic development, information society, knowledge economy, well-being of the population.*

Аннотация. *В экономической теории постиндустриального общества в качестве фактора производства выделяют информационный фактор. Он тесно связан с достижениями современной науки, оказывающей решающее воздействие на уровень эффективности производства, процесс подготовки квалифицированной рабочей силы и повышения потенциальных возможностей человеческого капитала. Информация обеспечивает систематизацию знаний, материализованных в систему механизмов и машин, оборудования, моделей менеджмента и маркетинга.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективность производственного процесса, интенсивное экономическое развитие, информационное общество, экономика знаний, благосостояние населения*

Annotatsiya. *Postindustrial jamiyatning iqtisodiy nazariyasida axborot omili ishlab chiqarish omili sifatida ajralib turadi. Bu ishlab chiqarish samaradorligi darajasiga, malakali ishchi kuchini tayyorlash jarayoniga va inson kapitali salohiyatini oshirishga hal qiluvchi ta'sir ko'rsatadigan zamonaviy ilm-fan yutuqlari bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Axborot mexanizmlar va mashinalar, uskunalar, boshqaruv va marketing modellari tizimiga kiritilgan bilimlarni tizimlashtirishni ta'minlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ishlab chiqarish jarayonining samaradorligi, intensiv iqtisodiy rivojlanish, axborot jamiyati, bilim iqtisodiyoti, aholi farovonligi*

Information as a factor of production is extremely necessary in modern conditions of functioning. It ensures the efficiency of decisions made, helps to develop entrepreneurial ability and increase the efficiency of the production process. The availability of information reduces the influence of such external factors as uncertainty. The theory of sustainable development is one of the complex concepts; it is designed to solve the problem of uncertainty in the development of the macroeconomic system in the long term. Initially, the category of “sustainable development” was proposed as a response to the environmental challenges of our time and was understood in the sense of a conscious focus of development on the long-term provision of humanity with sources of natural resources, provided that the environment is not destroyed. However, gradually, the views of scientists on this issue became broader, in connection with which there

were incentives to talk about the orientation of economic development to meet broad social needs, as well as to maintain the ability to meet similar needs of all future generations. Thus, the theory of sustainable development accumulates the provisions of theories of economic growth and development and is potentially capable of becoming a general theory of quantitative and qualitative economic development. Intensive economic development of many developed countries and their increasing involvement in the process of globalization has led to the emergence of terms such as "information society", "knowledge society". Currently, human capital and information resource have become the main factors in the development of modern society and the world economy as a whole. The information resource and the knowledge and information included in it are part of the accumulated and operating human capital, are its base and foundation. Computer scientists were the first to introduce the terms "information society" and "information economy" in relation to the most developed countries in the world.

The welfare levels of our state and many developed countries are different. We are at different stages of development; therefore, commodity relations have become a universal form of communication between individual counterparties that produce goods and services. At present, the main conditions that determine the well-being of an individual are his upbringing and education, respectively, the family and school are becoming the main social institutions that shape future well-being. No market mechanism can provide the consumer with a better and better life than he deserves in terms of his level of knowledge and degree of cultural education. Based on the received level of knowledge, a person forms a certain way of consumption, where the result should be the education of reasonable consumption. The result of creative work is the acquisition of information or knowledge. If the industrial era was characterized by the production and consumption of a material product, in the information society only that material product that will contribute to the development of the individual will be appreciated.

Information is largely a public good, and the act of recognizing a public good is its use in one form or another. In the production of goods and services, creativity is predominant. The result of creative work is the acquisition of information or knowledge. If the industrial era was characterized by the production and consumption of a material product, in the information society only that material product that will contribute to the development of the individual will be appreciated. In modern society, the functioning of the entire economic system will cause a change in the main characteristics of the goods dominating in society. With the development of the information society, material well-being will no longer be as dominant as it is at present. A condition for increasing welfare will be a certain period equal to the total duration of time for the implementation of "higher activity".

In the information society, the theory of welfare is being modified: it is creative work that will form non-economic welfare, based on the fact that self-affirmation, self-education is a perfect good for human activity as a person. Many factors affect the standard of living. If the standard of living is taken as an economic category, then it will be influenced by such factors as real wages, real incomes of the population, the minimum wage, the subsistence level, and if we take the generalized indicator, then the value of GDP per capita, the share of it costs for final consumption, etc. If the standard of living is considered in close relationship with the quality of life of the population, then it will be influenced by the development of infrastructure, the state of health of the population, the ecological state of the environment, the availability of free time for people, etc.

All of the above has a direct impact on the well-being of the population, changing and improving it. Previously, the level of socio-economic development of a society was not

measured by the total amount of time spent on creative activities of people. With the development of the information economy, welfare can be considered as a broad, capacious concept, which is a complex socio-economic phenomenon that unites and includes various characteristics of the style, lifestyle and quality of life of the population, which must be approached from a level point of view, taking into account, in addition, "the highest activity" in society. At the same time, total income is no longer seen as the main factor. It is presented as a necessary sub-factor for the development of higher activity, which contributes to an increase in the level of education and health of the individual. Raising the standard of living of the population is the most important direction in the development of the state as a whole, since a high standard of living helps to reduce socio-economic tension in the country, and to increase human satisfaction. A high level and quality of life allows an individual to more actively develop his spiritual and cultural human potential, to reveal himself as a person and always strives for improvement.

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